

ACTIVITIES OF REPRESENTATIVE OFFICES OF FOREIGN DIPLOMATIC AND INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Nuriddin Kolkanov,

Associate Professor of the International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan, Ph.D

Abstract: This article analyzes the legal basis for the activities of representative offices of foreign diplomatic and international organizations in order to achieve effective bilateral and multilateral cooperation between the Republic of Uzbekistan and foreign countries and international organizations.

Key words: foreign policy, international relations, diplomacy, representation, international organizations.

ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ ПРЕДСТАВИТЕЛЬСТВ ЗАРУБЕЖНЫХ ДИПЛОМАТИЧЕСКИХ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЙ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН

Нуриддин Колканов,

Доцент Международной исламской академии Узбекистана, PhD

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются правовые основы деятельности представительств иностранных дипломатических и международных организаций в целях достижения эффективного двустороннего и многостороннего сотрудничества Республики Узбекистан с зарубежными странами и международными организациями.

Ключевые слова: внешняя политика, международные отношения, дипломатия, представительство, международные организации.

O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDAGI XORIJIY DIPLOMATIK VA XALQARO TASHKILOTLAR VAKOLATXONALARI FAOLIYATI

Nuriddin Qolqanov,

O‘zbekiston xalqaro islom akademiyasi dotsenti, PhD

Аннотация: Мазкур мақолада Ўзбекистон Республикаси хорижий мамлакатлар ва халқаро ташкилотлар билан икки ва ко‘п томонлама самарали ҳамкорликка erishish maqsadida хорижий дипломатик ва халқаро ташкилотлар vakolatxonalari faoliyat yuritishining huquqiy asoslari tahlil etilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: tashqi siyosat, xalqaro munosabatlar, diplomatiya, vakolatxona, xalqaro tashkilotlar.

INTRODUCTION

In order to strengthen relations between states on the territory of foreign states, state bodies place special representative offices - diplomatic missions. According to international law, their commencement, closure, and even operation are of particular importance for any normal interstate relations.

The multifaceted integration of New Uzbekistan into the world community continues. Uzbekistan is a member of more than 100 international organizations, and our country is developing partnerships with multilateral cooperation structures at various levels. In general, Uzbekistan has currently established international legal relations with more than 230 international structures.

DISCUSSION

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

Accordingly, in order to regulate and improve the activities of diplomatic missions, consular offices of foreign states, representative offices of international organizations and their employees, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted Resolution No. 207 “On the activities of diplomatic missions, consular offices of foreign states, representative offices of international organizations and their employees in the Republic of Uzbekistan”¹.

According to the Regulation on Diplomatic Missions and Consular Institutions of Foreign States in the Republic of Uzbekistan, a diplomatic mission (embassy and mission) of a foreign state in the Republic of Uzbekistan, a consular institution (consulate general, vice-consulate or consular agency) of a foreign state in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as bodies of a foreign state, employees of diplomatic missions and employees of consular institutions are granted privileges and immunities for the performance of their functions, which are established in accordance with the Vienna Convention on Diplomatic Relations of April 18, 1961 and the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations of April 24, 1963, international customs, legislation and international treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Employees of diplomatic missions and consular offices, to whom privileges and immunities are granted, are obliged to respect the laws and regulations of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the culture, traditions, and customs of its people.

Currently, embassies are considered the highest form of diplomatic mission. Its establishment signifies the establishment of high-level diplomatic relations with a particular country.

In accordance with the Vienna Convention, the diplomatic, administrative-technical, and service personnel of the diplomatic mission perform the following functions:

- to be a representative of the accrediting state in the state of residence;
- to protect the interests of one's state and citizens in the state of residence within the framework of international law;
- to conduct negotiations with the government of the host state;
- to establish, by legal means, the conditions and events in the state in which it is located and inform the government of its state about them;
- maintaining friendly relations between their state and the state in which they are located, developing mutual ties in the sphere of economics, culture, and science (Article 3).

Diplomatic missions establish and maintain official relations with state bodies and institutions of the republic through the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The diplomatic mission has the right to:

- 1) head at the level of ambassadors, nunci, representatives, internunci under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- 2) the head at the level of authorized representatives is accredited to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The class of heads of diplomatic missions is determined between the respective states and the Republic of Uzbekistan. The head of the diplomatic mission or any member of the diplomatic staff may be accredited by the accredited state in another state or states with prior notification of this to the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The diplomatic mission instructs the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan to:

¹ <https://lex.uz/docs/-338699?ONDATE=05.04.2022%2000>

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

- on the appointment, arrival and departure of employees of the diplomatic mission or termination of their activities in the diplomatic mission;
- on the arrival and final departure of a person belonging to the family of a diplomatic mission employee;
- on the arrival and final departure of employees of the diplomatic mission, housekeepers;
- on the hiring and dismissal of persons residing in Uzbekistan as employees of diplomatic missions or domestic servants who have the right to benefits and immunity;
- on the intention to acquire or lease real estate for the placement of a diplomatic mission and the residence of the head of the mission;
- notifies the diplomatic staff of the mission in advance about their place of residence.

RESULTS

The accredited state cannot establish a chancellery, which is an integral part of the diplomatic mission, in other settlements of the republic without the consent of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The Diplomatic Corps Service Bureau of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan assists the diplomatic mission and its employees in the acquisition and lease of necessary real estate on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan in accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and also mediates the lease of premises from private individuals.

The buildings of diplomatic missions and the private residences of the heads of diplomatic missions, as well as the housing of members of diplomatic missions, are inviolable. Entry into the premises of diplomatic missions and the private residences of the heads of diplomatic missions, as well as into the residences of members of diplomatic missions, is permitted only with the consent of the head of the diplomatic mission of the respective foreign state.

A diplomatic mission may communicate freely with its government, other representative offices and consular offices of its state in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as other representative offices and consular offices of its state in third countries, by means of conventional means of communication, encoded and encrypted messages, as well as diplomatic mail.

Diplomatic missions may install and use wireless transmitters only with the permission of the competent authorities of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The archives, documents, and official correspondence of the diplomatic mission are inviolable at any time, regardless of their location.

Authorized bodies of state power assist and protect diplomatic couriers in the performance of their official duties to the extent possible.

Heads of diplomatic missions are exempt from all taxes, fees, and duties in respect of private or rented premises of diplomatic missions, with the exception of taxes, fees, and duties constituting payment for certain types of services, including rent.

The head of the diplomatic mission and members of the diplomatic staff are exempt from all taxes, fees, and duties, except for:

- taxes (value added tax, excise duties, customs duties), which are usually included in the price of goods or services;
- fees and taxes on the property of individuals located in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, if they do not own the property on behalf of the accredited state for the purposes of the representative office;
- state duties on inheritance;

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

fees and taxes on income with a source in the Republic of Uzbekistan, taxes on capital investments in commercial enterprises in the Republic of Uzbekistan;

fees levied on certain types of services;

property registration, court and registry fees.

The diplomatic mission may import and export goods intended for official use, and the head of the diplomatic mission and members of the diplomatic staff of the diplomatic mission - items intended for their personal use, including goods necessary for initial settlement.

Items intended for official use by a diplomatic mission, as well as goods intended for personal use by the head of the diplomatic mission and members of the diplomatic staff of the diplomatic mission, are exempt from all customs duties, taxes and fees, with the exception of payments for storage, outside designated places or customs clearance of items, subject to compliance with the established procedure for moving items across the customs border.

Personal baggage of the head of the diplomatic mission and members of the diplomatic staff is exempt from inspection, except for cases when there are grounds for the presence in the baggage of goods prohibited for import and export by the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Such inspection must be carried out only in the presence of baggage holders or their authorized representative.

The head of the diplomatic mission and members of the diplomatic staff enjoy the right to personal inviolability, and the Republic of Uzbekistan ensures the free movement of employees of diplomatic missions within its borders.

The head of the diplomatic mission and members of the diplomatic staff enjoy immunity from the criminal, civil, and administrative jurisdiction of the Republic of Uzbekistan, but these persons belong to the jurisdiction of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the express consent of the accrediting state.

CONCLUSION

The right of immunity from civil jurisdiction does not apply to cases when the head of the diplomatic mission and members of the diplomatic staff of the diplomatic mission enter into civil legal relations as private persons in connection with a claim for immovable property, inheritance belonging to them in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as in connection with claims arising from their professional or commercial activities carried out outside of their official duties.

The head of the diplomatic mission and members of the diplomatic mission are not obliged to give testimony as witnesses, and if they agree to give such testimony, they are not obliged to appear for this in court or investigative bodies.

REFERENCES:

1. Yangi tahrirdagi O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi (Qonunchilik ma'lumotlari milliy bazasi, 01.05.2023-y., 03/23/837/0241-son) // <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-6445145>
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasining O'RQ-330-sonli Qonuni bilan tasdiqlangan O'zbekiston Respublikasining Tashqi siyosiy faoliyati konsepsiyasi (Qonun hujjatlari ma'lumotlari milliy bazasi, 11.09.2012-y., 03/19/338/2589-son) // <https://www.lex.uz/docs/-29415935>
3. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyevning Oliy Majlis Qonunchilik palatasining birinchi yig'ilishidagi nutqi // <https://president.uz>.
4. Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties: <https://legal.un.org/ilc/texts/instruments/english/conventions/>

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

5. Юнусов Х. Конституционные основы внешней политики Республики Узбекистан // Review of law sciences. 2020. Спецвыпуск.

6. Kolkanov, N. (2024). USE OF DIFFERENT TECHNOLOGIES IN FORMING AND IMPROVING THE IMAGE OF A POLITICAL LEADER. *Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 11(05), 565-568.

7. Колканов, Н. Т. (2018). Процесс формирования имиджа политического лидера (опыт Узбекистана). Редакционная коллегия, 157.

